

inhabiting

body-territories

in the datafied city

a Zine about embodiment

November 2024

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 873119.

Co-funded by
the European Union

a b o u t

Dear Reader,

This is a fanzine. A fanzine, or *zine*, is a self-published material inspired by the Do-It-Yourself (DIY) idea. I have produced this fanzine to disseminate what I learned and found during my two-month research stay at Instituto Mora, located in Mexico City, thanks to the support of the PRODIGEES project.

I was in Mexico from July to September 2024 to exchange with researchers, social movements, and activists so that I could elaborate further on the concept of body-territory as a tool to understand how data-driven urbanism enacts different bodies in the cities.

Inspired by workshops I attended during my research stay, this fanzine is a digital collage of notes, references, ideas, insights, and, why not, affections and memories. Those pieces put together a collective learning process around the topics I was dedicated to.

This is a summary of reflections on the possibilities brought by the increasing datafication of cities. In this sense, this work claims that departing from the body as the first scale of territoriality is an essential starting point for thinking about urban data.

As a Latin American researcher in diaspora, I hope this humble work also crosses borders and boundaries, breaking walls to foster a dialogue about other ways of living in the big data era.

I hope you enjoy reading it. We keep in touch.

Rafaela Cavalcanti de Alcantara
Vienna, Autumn 2024

Here, you find a view from a body,* my body. Thus, the following considerations are influenced by the fact that I am a Latin American female who has migrated to Central Europe. Like everybody else, I have my world views and political positions, which also inform my research activities. Presenting research findings as a fanzine is also affected by the idea that every scientific and/or technology production is situated and partial. Thus, Science and Technology will always be socio-politically situated, even if this is not confessed.

* see Haraway, 1988

what places
does one
occupy in the
world?

Living is occupying places: cities, lands, streets, neighbourhoods, homes. Even if it is dangerous, even if it is forbidden. Those who migrate do so by occupying places beyond borders and boundaries. One *has* to occupy land to live, find shelter, and be with their loved ones. One *has* to occupy the world to work even if not adequately paid for the work done. Historically, groups have occupied streets to claim rights, demand laws, demote laws, question power, fight governments, complain about governments, stand for their positions, denounce, complain, and mourn.

And also to party, celebrate their lives and express joy & love.

For instance: over the years, women and other people with uteruses in Argentina occupied the streets with their bodies to demand rights concerning those very bodies.

In December 2020, the right to legal abortion was approved by the Senate. The use of green *pañuelos* marked the protests that occupied the streets, so the movement is also known as the *Marea Verde* (Green Wave) in Latin America.

both photos taken in Santa Fe, Argentina (2018)

The bodies making the *Marea Verde* illustrate the body as each one's first territoriality to struggle for. These are the bodies that need to fight to exist, to occupy the world, and to move around. The majority of the bodies in the world are involved in struggles of this kind, although those journeys are often erased or invisibilized.

collective bodies

Here, I am echoing feminist claims. There is no such thing as an 'abstract' human being because those abstractions lead to an imagined-universal-person or group of people. Likewise, there is no such thing as an 'ideal' urban citizen living in the urban world. On the contrary, (different) bodies form collectivities with (specific) necessities and capabilities when *inhabiting* a city.

Picture of a #NiUnaMenos march in Lima, Peru (2016)

I am referring to materialities. So, I call attention to the bodies that do not easily access *Liberté, Égalité* and *Fraternité*; the bodies that are seen as the 'others,' whose needs are placed on the margins.

"Marcos is gay in San Francisco, black in South Africa, an Asian in Europe, a Chicano in San Ysidro, an anarchist in Spain, a Palestinian in Israel, a Mayan Indigenous on the streets of San Cristobal, a Jew in Germany, a Romani in Poland, a Mohawk in Quebec, a pacifist in Bosnia, a single woman on the Metro at 10 p.m., a peasant without land, a gang member in the slums, an unemployed worker, an unhappy student and, of course, a Zapatista in the mountains." – Subcomandante Marcos

From Chiapas, Subcomandante Marcos' words refer to the complexity and relationality of living in the world. In a poetical-political manner, the Subcomandante illustrates the transnationality of Zapatista's claims.

Graffiti in
El Mourouj,
Tunis,
Tunisia (2012)

DE CAMINO A
CASA QUIERO
SE LIBRE
NO VALIENTE
#NIUNAMENOS

"On my way home
I want to be
free not
brave," says a
intervention in
Rancagua, Chile
(2019)

Thinking that there is no standardized inhabitant in the city is remembering that people inhabit the city firstly through their bodies. But why is it important to consider this?

Because bodies are diverse, carry out different activities and have specific needs in the urban space. Trans, nonbinary, racialized, female, feminized, and queer bodies have different perceptions of safety and freedom when walking on the streets or taking public transportation at night. Because bodies that carry out sexual, informal, or low- and unpaid work have their demands regarding the common spaces of the city. Because bodies marching may be violently repressed. Because some of the bodies are labeled and targeted by State forces.

**Living in the urban world
is also embodying the city.**

Body-territory is a call, an idea, and an epistemology coming from indigenous struggles in Latin America. The term exposes how the exploitation of the common - like the land and the water - affects each person's as well as the collective body. *Body-territory* also remembers that both body and territory are not neutral categories.

on body- territory

If occupying the city with the body generates an entanglement of meanings, demands and necessities, *body-territory* calls attention to the centrality of the community. In this sense, *body-territory* challenges the liberal idea of the 'individual,' also thinking about the collective effects of extractivism(s) - which may include, for instance, *data extractivism*.

Al habitar las tienditas, los comercios, las fondas, los cafés entre otros espacios de nuestros barrios, formamos relaciones de confianza con aquellas personas que son parte de la comunidad.

The sentence written on the bottom of the artwork has especially caught my attention:

La tienda de la esquina,
by Rafael Álvarez Díaz.
National Museum of Housing (Museo Nacional de la Vivienda - Munavi), Mexico

"Al habitar las tienditas, los comercios, las fondas, los cafés entre otros espacios de nuestros barrios, formamos relaciones de confianza con aquellas personas que son parte de la comunidad"
["As we inhabit the small shops, stores, fondas, cafes, and other spaces in our neighbourhoods, we form relationships of trust with those who are part of the community"].

Inhabiting creates a familiar connection to pieces of the city: places, communities, people. Therefore, there is a mesh of relations flourishing from inhabiting.

While living in a city, each body touches diverse human and non-human worlds. Those connections are related to the possibilities of working, studying, struggling, organizing, getting pleasure, and enjoying the urban space.

I also had the opportunity to visit Frida Kahlo's museum, *la Casa Azul*, the artist's home for most of her life. The museum's narrative approaches some of the places Frida inhabited.

According to the museum, the house consisted of "a window to the world." It helps to visualize the position from which Kahlo stood and inhabited through feelings, arts, studies, and pain.

Moreover, the museum advances towards the body Frida inhabited, emphasizing how her embodied conditions informed her life, work, and relationships.

Some of Frida's prosthetics and orthopaedic corsets are exhibited there. A leg prosthesis Frida wore is displayed, followed by a quote from her diaries: "*Pies para qué los quiero si tengo alas para volar*" ["Feet, what do I need you for when I have wings to fly"].

Frida wore corsets to help her spine to stand. She also used those apparatuses as canvases, where she expressed, among other ideas, political statements.

In 1954, Frida would paint *El marxismo dará salud a los enfermos* [Marxism will heal the sick], where she portrayed her body in the center between crutches, wearing an orthopaedic vest.

Those representations portray the body as a basis for expression and...

the body as a political body.

America Invertida, by Joaquín Torres García (1943)

Body-territory is about a gaze, a position, a way of seeing.* If we think about inhabiting a datafied city, it is necessary to consider something that applies to disputes around living in the urban space: body-territories are political, just as the choices that shape urban policies. So, since cities are not neutral spaces, there is no single way to use big data to manage them.

The possibility of building a city according to the people we want to be is one of the ideas of the Right to the City.** Therefore, I am referring to the possibilities of interfering in the urban space.

Data have always been informing urban policies.*** But I am talking here about *big data* - the every-moment generation of large amounts of data about various aspects. I also note the abstractions, seductions and illusions emerging from big data hegemonic narratives.

From online digital dashboards accessed via portable computers to operations rooms where hundreds of people work 24/7, choices that impact body-territories in the city intend to translate urban life into data. Databases may try to represent the traffic, crowds, public transportation, or faces to be identified.

bodies in datafied spaces

When people *inhabit* a place, knowledge about this place is produced. Inhabiting generates an understanding of the city we live in and the changes we want to make. Thus, some questions must be asked before taking for granted that big data is the most accurate way to represent reality.*

How are the databases situated?

Who manages those databases?

On behalf of whose interests?

Do body-territories in the city have the opportunity to debate and choose how big data will inform urban policies?

Is (big)data-based knowledge prioritized over other kinds of knowledge?

* See Ricaurte 2019

“cambia, todo cambia”

Bodies inhabit a city by connecting relationships between the body and other human and non-human worlds. Visualizing it is also viewing what is often omitted from official narratives.

Seeing the body-territories in the datafied city also allows us to think about other worlds, which materializes in other possibilities of living in cities.

To imagine other ways to inhabit the city, it is necessary to perceive big data narratives beyond their promises.

From that, the possibility of preventing technologies from potentializing existing oppressions is born; also, we will be able to debate the appropriation of technological tools on behalf of our collective bodies.

Cambia lo superficial / Cambia también lo profundo / Cambia el modo de pensar / Cambia todo en este mundo [...] – Todo Cambia is a song written by Julio Numhauser and sung by Mercedes Sosa

CuERPAS

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acknowledgements

The findings summarized in this fanzine could only be elaborated on with the generosity of many interlocutors. In this sense, I thank those people who, directly or indirectly, helped me to navigate my research stay in Mexico City. Thus, I am profoundly grateful:

To people who nicely gave me directions while I was moving around in Mexico City, one of the most amazing places I have been. Also, I express my gratitude to the fellow anonymous interlocutors I have exchanged ideas with on the streets or during workshops.

To the staff at Instituto Mora, who supported my stay and made it even more meaningful. In this sense, I especially thank Citlali Ayala Martínez, Constanza Larenas, Dr. Isela Orihuela, José Félix Farachala, Dr. Juan Carlos Domínguez, Dr. Kristina Pirker, Dr. Luisa Fernanda Rodríguez Cortés, Dr. Mateo Crossa Niell, and Selene Acosta. I also thank the staff members responsible for keeping the institute's facilities clean and organized.

To the Center for Gender Researches and Studies of the National Autonomous University of Mexico (Centro de Investigaciones y Estudios de Género - CIEG, UNAM), especially Dr. César Torres Cruz, Dr. Fabiola Buenrostro, and Gisel Tovar, in addition to the colleagues I met at CIEG's activities. I cannot imagine my stay without your workshops, Fanzinoteca, and friendly generosity and attention. *Mil gracias, Muitíssimo obrigada!*

For the talks, recommendations, and insights I have had while talking to Dr. Andrea Vera Gajardo, Dr. Elsa Muñiz García, and Dr. Raúl Cabrera, who generously offered their time to listen to me and share fruitful considerations about my research goals.

To the staff and instructors of the museums I visited as part of my research stay. In this sense, I want to mention the super considerate staff of the National Museum of Housing (Museo Nacional de la Vivienda - Munavi).

To the PRODIGEES team at IDOS, in the name of the project manager who has been supporting my activities directly, Benjamin Stewart.

To Barbara Saringer-Bory, Benedikt Wildner, Dr. Doris Allhutter, and Dr. Mahshid Sotoudeh, who amazingly supported my research visit from ITA.

Last but not least, to my colleagues Saskia Favreuille and Sara Ortega Ramirez, who kindly exchanged ideas with me about my fanzine endeavours.

Every knowledge production is a collective work, but please note that mistakes or misconceptions this fanzine may present are my sole responsibility.

credits

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